

Embracing thermophotovoltaic electricity: Pathways to market adoption

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Thermophotovoltaics
Thermal batteries
Markets
Technoeconomics
Applications
Levelized Cost of Electricity
LCOE

ABSTRACT

Thermophotovoltaic (TPV) energy conversion has gained significant attention in recent years, leading to the funding of numerous research and business initiatives, particularly in Europe and the US. This growing interest stems from the remarkable efficiency of TPV devices, which can convert radiant heat directly into electricity with efficiencies exceeding 40%. This positions TPV as the most efficient solid-state heat engine, with the potential to outperform traditional turbogenerators. This article explores the techno-economic parameters essential for the profitability of TPV systems and examines their primary applications and future research challenges. It begins by outlining the key factors influencing TPV viability, including electric power density, cost per unit area, and TPV cell efficiency. Using the levelized cost of electricity as a central framework, the study identifies suitable applications for TPV technology, emphasizing its potential in military and space applications, waste heat recovery, and thermal energy storage. Finally, the article addresses ongoing research challenges, detailing innovations in TPV technology that could significantly reduce costs and expand its applicability across a wider range of heat source temperatures. The study concludes that the development of TPV batteries—systems that store surplus electricity as ultra-high-temperature heat and reconvert it into electricity using TPV technology—represents a unique opportunity for TPV to move beyond niche applications and toward broader commercial viability.

1. Introduction

The conversion of heat into electricity serves as the cornerstone of modern economies, accounting for the majority of the world's electric power generation. This encompasses both non-renewable sources such as gas, coal, and nuclear energy, as well as renewable sources like solar thermal power plants. Moreover, it plays a pivotal role in industrial waste heat recovery initiatives and holds potential as a key component in the energy harvesting capabilities of next-generation thermal batteries. Nearly all heat engines currently in operation are dynamic systems, which entail the generation of mechanical energy—typically in the form of working fluid flow—as an intermediary step in the conversion of heat into electricity. A remarkable feature of these systems is that they are cost-effective only at large scales [1], and this partially explains why today's energy systems rely on large scale and centralized power plants.

In contrast to dynamic systems, solid-state thermal-to-electric energy converters (STEC) facilitate modular, noiseless energy conversion without moving parts, with a crucial feature being their conversion efficiency, which remains largely independent of size. Consequently, they enable small-scale and decentralized electricity generation from

dispersed sources of heat. Approximately 70% of global primary energy consumption is lost after transport and conversion, with much of this energy dissipated into heat in various sectors such as transport, residential, industry and power generation plants [2]. In this context, STEC technology offers the potential to harness scattered waste heat and convert it into electricity, thereby enhancing the overall efficiency of the global energy system. Moreover, heat constitutes approximately 50% of the final energy demand in the EU, underscoring its importance in future energy systems [3]. As heat production shifts towards decentralized and variable renewable energy sources like solar or wind, the development of new thermal energy storage and sector-coupling devices becomes imperative to facilitate on-demand heat and electricity generation across various scales. In this regard, STEC devices are poised to emerge as key sector-couplers bridging distributed heat and electricity energy networks, thereby unlocking new opportunities and revenue streams within the interconnected energy systems of the future.

Among all STEC alternatives, thermoelectric generators (TEG) have gained the most attention (and funding) in recent decades [4,5]. TEG operates on the principle of electron flow through a solid medium, driven by a temperature gradient. However, a fundamental challenge

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solmat.2025.113419>

Received 5 October 2024; Received in revised form 31 December 2024; Accepted 7 January 2025

Available online 31 January 2025

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faced by TEG is the trade-off between the (useful) electron energy flux and the (useless) phonon energy flux, commonly referred to as heat conduction losses, within the solid material. Traditionally, addressing this issue involves the quest for materials exhibiting very low thermal conductivity (κ), high electrical conductivity (σ), and high Seebeck coefficient (S), collectively quantified by the thermoelectric merit function $ZT = (\sigma S^2 T)/\kappa$. Despite decades of intensive research, this approach is hindered by inherent limitations stemming from the natural trade-off between these parameters in solid materials. Notably, thermal and electrical conductivities are intricately linked, so that a paramount challenge is to reduce one (thermal conductivity) while simultaneously increasing the other (electrical conductivity). Consequently, the maximum conversion efficiencies of TEGs have yet to surpass 15 % [1, 6]. Some recent papers have highlighted the potential of new materials such as 2D topological insulators (e.g. Stanene, Bismuthene, WTe_2) that can reach larger conversion efficiencies, but they are only at the very early stage of research and quite far from potential applications considering the strong issues in producing suitable materials [7–10].

Thermophotovoltaic (TPV) devices represent a solid-state alternative to thermoelectrics, directly converting radiant heat into electricity [11, 12]. The absence of solid continuity between the hot and cold reservoirs allows for lower heat losses and enhanced conversion efficiencies. Remarkably, TPV has emerged as the most efficient solid-state heat engine, achieving efficiencies in the range of 30–44 % at radiant emitter temperatures spanning from 1000 to 2400 °C [13–18] (Fig. 1). This efficiency is already in the range of more established turbogenerators (Fig. 2), paving the way for efficient decentralized thermal-to-electric energy conversion applications.

Research on TPV devices commenced in the late 1950s and early 1960s under US army contracts [19], aiming to develop a silent and lightweight portable generator. However, the lack of high-quality TPV cells hindered any successful demonstration, leading to the widespread adoption of thermoelectric generators for those applications [20]. In the early 1990s, a renewed interest in TPV technology emerged, partially driven by the availability of highly efficient infrared-sensitive PV cells, primarily GaSb [21], and InGaAs [22], initially designed as bottom subcells for multijunction tandem solar cells. These technological advancements culminated in the first reported TPV thermal-to-electric conversion efficiency of 23.6 % in 2004 [23]. Twenty years later, further improvements in cell technology have resulted in new record TPV efficiency of 44 % [18]. The key to achieving such high efficiency lies in the incorporation of a highly reflective mirror at the rear of the TPV cell, redirecting outband energy photons back to the thermal emitter. Theoretical calculations suggest that efficiencies exceeding 60

Fig. 2. Historical evolution of the conversion efficiency of different thermal-to-electric energy converters. Adapted from Ref. [29]. In recent years TPV cells have surpassed the efficiency of steam turbines in converting radiant heat into electricity and have become the most efficient heat engine at small scales.

% could be achievable by exceeding an outband reflectance of 99 % [24].

The advantages of TPV technology, compared to more established turbogenerators, stem from its high efficiency, especially at smaller scales. It also lacks moving parts, and it is capable of operating at very high temperatures. Furthermore, the cost per power capacity of TPV can be lower than or comparable to that of conventional turbogenerators (ranging from 1 to 10 €/W [25]), provided the operating temperature—and consequently the power density—are sufficiently high.

Nevertheless, despite the encouraging results and future potential, TPV technology is currently facing cost-performance issues that preclude their full deployment. Therefore, it is crucial to start progressing through the learning curve and further reduce the cost of the technology. To that end, the identification of the proper and most profitable applications for TPV technology is a crucial aspect. The purpose of this article is triggering this discussion.

Fig. 1. State of the art efficiency (a) and electric power density (b) of TPV cells. Adapted from Ref. [26]. Additional works added to the figure with respect to Ref. [26] are the ones by Roy Layinde [18], Dashiell [27], and Fraas [28], as reported in Ref. [12].

2. Performance and cost metrics in TPV systems and applications

Before delving into potential applications of the TPV technology, it is pertinent to understand the parameters that determine its profitability. To that end, Fig. 3 illustrates the energy flows and cost metrics of a complete TPV system and Table 1 categorizes these metrics into thermal and TPV sub-systems.

Among all the parameters listed in Table 1, the $LCOE_{tpv}$ stands as the paramount metric for TPV electricity generation, as it directly dictates the payback period of the investment. A TPV system can be considered economically viable when its payback period is shorter than the expected operational lifetime of the installation—that is, when the $LCOE_{tpv}$ falls below the average price of the alternative source of electricity (e.g., the grid) over the same period. Several prior studies have utilized the LCOE to examine the techno-economic aspects of TPV systems, especially in TPV batteries [30,31]. Notably, a recent work by Verma et al. [32] presents an extensive analysis of TPV applications based on LCOE.

By disregarding maintenance expenditures and assuming a power generation capacity with no degradation over time, the LCOE of TPV electricity can be formulated as follows [30,33] (see Appendix 1):

$$LCOE_{tpv} = \frac{CPP_{tpv}^*}{t_{eq,tpv}} + \frac{LCOeH}{\eta_{tpv}} \quad (1)$$

In this expression CPP_{tpv}^* is the annualized cost per power capacity of the TPV cell that is obtained from the initial capital expenditure CPP_{tpv} as $CPP_{tpv}^* = CPP_{tpv} \cdot r(1+r)^n / ((1+r)^n - 1)$, being r the discount rate and n the lifetime of the installation (in years). In the equation, $t_{eq,tpv}$ is the number of hours of operation during a year equivalent to continuous loading at rated capacity. It is related to the capacity factor (CF), which is defined as the ratio between the actual net thermal energy delivered to the TPV converter and the energy that could have been delivered at continuous rated power operation during a certain period of time (i.e. $CF = t_{eq,tpv}/8760$).

Equation (1) reveals that the LCOE comprises two primary contributions: capital expenditures or CAPEX (first term) and operational

expenditures or OPEX (second term). The OPEX term corresponds to the Levelized Cost of Absorbed Radiant Heat (LCOeH). To clarify our rationale, we assign an OPEX term to the absorbed photons despite their generation relying on CAPEX-intensive components (e.g., thermal emitters, heating elements, or thermal energy storage materials). This assignment emphasizes that, from the TPV cell's perspective, any process involved in generating photons directly contributes to its operational cost, thereby justifying the inclusion of an OPEX term in the formulation.

In applications where LCOeH is non-negligible (such as in thermal batteries or fuel-fired systems), achieving high TPV cell efficiency (η_{tpv}) is crucial to mitigate its impact on the LCOE. However, in scenarios where LCOeH is negligible (such as industrial waste heat), TPV can accommodate lower conversion efficiencies. In such cases, the primary requirement for TPV technology is to ensure a very low CAPEX contribution, characterized by a low annualized cost per power (CPP_{TPV}^*) and a large number of equivalent operation hours ($t_{eq,tpv}$). This underscores the varying technological requirements depending on the specific market application.

The LCOeH varies depending on the applications and it can be formulated as a function of several factors. In the most generic case depicted in Fig. 3, these include the levelized cost of input energy ($LCOE_{in}$, in €/Wh), the heating (or charging) efficiency (η_{ht}), the annualized cost per power capacity of the heating system (CPP_{ht}^* , in €/W), and the annualized cost of the thermal emitter (CPP_{emit}^* , in €/W_{th}). Moreover, if the system includes thermal storage capacity, the LCOeH also depends on the storage efficiency (η_{st}), the number of full charges per year (N_c) and the annualized cost per energy storage capacity (CPE^* , in €/Wh). According to the definition of LCOeH, which accounts for the cost of net radiant thermal energy absorbed in the TPV cell, it will also depend on the thermal efficiency of the TPV converter η_{th} (see Appendix 1):

$$LCOeH = \frac{1}{\eta_{th}} \left[LCOH + \frac{CPP_{emit}^*}{t_{eq,tpv}} \right] \\ = \frac{1}{\eta_{th}} \left[\frac{LCOE_{in}}{\eta_{ht}\eta_{st}} + \frac{CPP_{ht}^*}{\eta_{ht}\eta_{st}t_{eq,ht}} + \frac{CPE^*}{\eta_{st}N_c} + \frac{CPP_{emit}^*}{t_{eq,tpv}} \right] \quad (2)$$

Equation (2) depicts LCOeH as the sum of various terms, with the first

Fig. 3. Energy flows and cost metrics for a generic TPV system. Q_{in} is the input energy to the system, η_{ht} is the heating efficiency, η_{st} is the storage efficiency, η_{th} is the TPV thermal efficiency, η_{tpv} is the TPV cell conversion efficiency, and t_c/t_d is the ratio between the charging and discharging durations (if thermal storage is present). CPP_{ht} , CPP_{emit} , and CPP_{tpv} , refers to the cost per power capacity of the heating system, the emitter, and the TPV cell, respectively, and CPE refers to the cost per energy capacity of thermal energy storage system (if present). $LCOE_{in}$ and $LCOE_{tpv}$ are the levelized cost of energy input and output, respectively, whereas $LCOH$ and $LCOeH$ refers to the levelized cost of heat and absorbed radiant heat in the cell, respectively.

Table 1
Key techno-economic parameters to describe TPV electricity generation.

Thermal sub-system metrics	
Input energy (Q_m in W)	Depending on the application, various forms of input energy can be used to heat the system, such as solar energy, fuel combustion, industrial waste heat, electricity, or nuclear power.
Levelized cost of input energy (LCOE _{in} , in €/Wh)	It represents the average net present cost of the input energy delivered to the system. This cost can range from nearly zero, as in the case of solar energy or waste heat, to significant amounts in systems powered by fuel or electricity.
Heating efficiency (η_{ht})	It accounts for all types of losses during the conversion of input energy (Q_m) into internal thermal energy within the system. In open systems with an external heat source (e.g., fuel- or solar-powered systems), these losses can be significant due to the open channel allowing energy to flow in and out of the system (such as an open aperture in solar-powered systems or exhaust gases in fuel-powered systems). In contrast, in closed or quasi-closed systems with an internal heat source (e.g., nuclear or electric-powered thermal batteries), these losses may be very low.
Cost per power capacity of the heating system (CPP_{ht} , in €/W)	This includes all capital expenditures associated with generating and transferring high temperatures from the input energy, such as concentrating mirrors and absorbers for solar thermal devices, electric heaters for electro-thermal batteries, or burners for fuel-powered systems.
Cost per energy capacity of the thermal storage system (CPE, in €/Wh _{th})	This includes all capital expenditures related to the storage of high-temperature heat, such as the thermal storage media (e.g., carbon, silicon, ceramics, etc.) and thermal insulation materials.
Storage efficiency (η_{st})	This refers to thermal insulation losses, which increase with storage temperature but decrease with the system's scale (storage capacity) and energy density. In systems with large energy capacity and high energy density, these losses can be minimal, regardless of the storage temperature [30].
Levelized Cost of Heat (LCOH, in €/Wh _{th}):	This represents the average net present cost of the net thermal energy delivered to the TPV emitter. It is calculated as the ratio of the total annualized cost for heat generation to the total net heat supplied to the emitter. The Levelized Cost of Heat (LCOH) accounts for all expenditures required to generate high-temperature thermal energy, including the cost of energy input (LCOE _{in}), maintenance, and all capital expenditures associated with the generation, transfer, and storage of thermal energy (CPP_{ht} and CPE).
TPV sub-system metrics	
TPV thermal efficiency (η_{th})	This represents the ratio between the total absorbed heat in the TPV cell and the total heat rate delivered by the emitter, expressed as $\eta_{th} = (P_{el} + Q_{abs}) / (P_{el} + Q_{abs} + Q_{loss})$. In this equation, P_{el} is the electric power generated by the cell, Q_{abs} is the heat absorbed by the cell, and Q_{loss} is the heat lost to other parts of the system rather than being absorbed by the TPV cell. Therefore, thermal efficiency is maximized by effectively directing heat to the converter and minimizing heat leakages (Q_{loss}) in the system, such as optical losses in the cavity and thermal bridges in the emitter.
TPV cell conversion efficiency (η_{tpv})	This represents the ratio between electrical power output (P_{el}) and the total absorbed heat in the TPV cell ($P_{el} + Q_{abs}$), expressed as

Table 1 (continued)

Thermal sub-system metrics	
	$\eta_{tpv} = P_{el} / (P_{el} + Q_{abs})$. The dissipated heat density in the TPV cells (Q_{abs}) can be reduced by minimizing outband radiative photonic absorption, such as by incorporating high quality reflectors on the rear of the cell. However, reflected radiation must be recycled by the thermal emitter. Otherwise, it will contribute to deteriorate the TPV thermal efficiency (η_{th}).
Cost per power capacity of the TPV emitter (CPP_{emit} , in €/W _{th})	This includes all capital expenditures required to produce 1 W of radiative thermal power with the TPV emitter. Neglecting the cost associated with the balance of systems, CPP_{emit} can be calculated by dividing the cost per area (CPA_{emit} , in €/cm ²) by the radiative power density of the TPV emitter, i.e. $CPP_{emit} = CPA_{emit} / P_{emit}$.
Cost per power capacity of the TPV converter (CPP_{tpv} , in €/W _{el})	This includes all the capital expenditures incurred to produce 1 W of electric power with the TPV converter. Neglecting the cost associated with the balance of systems, CPP_{tpv} can be calculated by dividing the cost per area (CPA_{tpv} , in €/cm ²) by the electric power density of the TPV device (P_{el} , in W/cm ²), i.e. $CPP_{tpv} = CPA_{tpv} / P_{el}$.
Levelized Cost of Absorbed Radiative Heat (LCO _{RH} , in €/Wh _{th}):	This represents the average net present cost of the net radiant thermal energy absorbed by the TPV cell and is influenced by the levelized cost of incoming heat (LCOH), the cost of the thermal emitter and the thermal efficiency (η_{th}). Due to the significant cost of the emitter and the fact that $\eta_{th} \leq 1$, the LCO _{RH} is always greater than or equal to the LCOH.
Levelized cost of output electricity (LCOE _{tpv} , in €/Wh _{el})	This represents the average net present cost of the electricity produced by the TPV device. It is calculated as the ratio of the total annualized cost of the TPV system, including both capital investment and operational costs, to the total electricity generated.

one denoting OPEX and the final three representing CAPEX. Mitigating the influence of power subsystems CAPEX (CPP_{ht}^* and CPP_{emit}^*) necessitates a substantial number of operating hours ($t_{eq,ht}$ and $t_{eq,TPV}$), whereas countering the impact of energy-subsystem (thermal storage) CAPEX (CPE^*) requires a significant number of cycles (N_c). Additionally, attaining high storage efficiency (η_{st}) is essential for minimizing the impact of OPEX and both heating and storage subsystem CAPEX. Finally, achieving high heating efficiency (η_{ht}) is crucial for attenuating the effects of both OPEX and heating subsystem CAPEX. Because each system configuration utilizes different subsystems, different strategies must be employed to minimize the LCO_{RH} based on the specific application and overall system configuration.

It is important to note that CPP and CPE variables in Equations (1) and (2) cannot be determined without knowing the precise operating conditions of the system, like the radiative and electric power densities, which depend on both subsystem efficiencies and system dynamics. For the purposes of this article, we assume that the TPV system's operating conditions are known and identical during the lifetime of the installation, allowing for the calculation of appropriate values for CPP and CPE in Equations (1) and (2).

3. TPV markets and applications

In this section, we will analyze several potential TPV markets, and we will utilize the LCOE_{tpv} (equations (1) and (2)) as the central theme to determine suitable applications for TPV.

3.1. Space and military

The most apparent initial application of TPV arises in scenarios where cost considerations are not paramount. Examples of such scenarios include military [34] and space applications [20], where the absence of moving parts, silent operation, high conversion efficiency, and low weight make TPV devices advantageous compared to alternative technologies like thermoelectrics (which exhibit low efficiency) and Stirling generators (known for their moving parts, weight, and noise). These applications primarily focus on portable power generators, whether on Earth or in space, and utilize fuels—either chemical or nuclear—for heat generation. These were the main applications during the early years of TPV development [19], and they are still pursued today by some companies like Mesodyne® and JXCrystals®.

In space applications, the potentially high specific power (in W/kg) of TPV devices is a key advantage [20]. However, maintaining a low TPV cell temperature imposes stringent requirements on the cooling system, which can significantly increase the system's total weight. For example, a hypothetical 1 kW radioisotope TPV space power generator would require only about 0.3 m² of TPV cell area (assuming a 0.6 eV TPV cell and an emitter temperature of 1038 °C). However, cooling the cells would necessitate approximately 17 m² of radiator surface area [20]. Despite this, the resulting specific power is estimated to be around 7–9 W/kg, still significantly higher than that of conventional radioisotope thermoelectric generators (2.8–5.1 W/kg).

In terrestrial applications, cooling TPV cells is more straightforward due to the availability of practical solutions such as convective air coolers or forced water cooling systems. The key advantage of portable TPV generators in these settings lies in their high gravimetric energy density (in Wh/kg), resulting from the combination of high TPV conversion efficiency and the exceptional energy density of fuel (approaching 13 kWh/kg). This combination can yield an electric energy density in the range of 600–700 Wh_{el}/kg [35], surpassing the energy density of current state-of-the-art commercial Li-ion batteries, which reach up to 300 Wh_{el}/kg [36]. Recent advancements in TPV cell efficiency are expected to further increase the achievable energy density, reinforcing the potential of TPV technology for portable power generation.

3.2. Waste heat recovery

The next logical application of TPV technology is waste heat recovery. TPV cells could, for example, be employed to generate electricity from the thermal radiation emitted during the continuous casting of hot-rolled steel plates, which typically occurs at temperatures between 1000 and 1200 °C [37–39]. Other applications include flue gas heat recovery from industrial processes such as blast furnaces, re-melting, holding, heat treatment, secondary refining, and reheating furnaces. Wall heat recovery from high-temperature environments like electric arc furnaces also presents a viable opportunity for TPV integration [38].

In the context of waste heat recovery, the absence of heating and energy storage subsystems, combined with the negligible cost of waste heat, results in a negligible LCOH (see Equation (2)). As a result, efficiency becomes less critical in achieving a low LCOE_{tpv} (see Equation (1)), with the primary focus shifting to reducing the cost per power capacity of the TPV converter. Therefore, cheaper and less-efficient semiconductor materials could be utilized.

For instance, a silicon solar cell (bandgap energy of 1.12 eV), costing roughly 0.5 c€/cm², could potentially produce approximately 50 mW/cm² when fully illuminated (view factor of 1) by a 1000 °C black body emitter, resulting in a cost per power of only 0.1 €/W. This is twice the power and half the cost of the same solar cell under non-concentrated solar irradiation. Despite the promising cost-to-power ratio of silicon PV cells, the majority of CAPEX in this context will likely arise from balance-of-system (BOS) components. Operating the solar cells at such elevated thermal loads (a thermal emitter at 1000 °C radiates nearly

150 kW/m² of thermal power), requires significant adaptations. Potential requirements include active water-cooling systems and optical filters to reduce thermal absorption, or protective refractory shields to mitigate condensation of undesirable by-products on the PV cells. Other components such as power electronics, structural mounts, piping, and other auxiliary equipment will also contribute to BOS costs. For example, if a target total CAPEX of 10 €/W—comparable to that of turbogenerators—is set, a maximum of 9.9 €/W, equivalent to 4950 € per square meter, could be allocated for BOS implementation.

A viable strategy to relax BOS cost constraints is increasing the power density of the TPV generator. In the previous example, doubling the power density from 50 to 100 mW/cm²—while keeping the PV cell cost constant—would allow a BOS expenditure of up to 9950 € per square meter while keeping the total CAPEX at 10 €/W. However, this strategy is only valid if the increase in the power density does not significantly increase the cost per power of the TPV cell.

In this context, Germanium (bandgap energy of 0.67 eV) emerges as an appealing semiconductor with relatively low-cost (if compared to other low-bandgap semiconductors) that also produces significant power from infrared thermal radiation. Germanium is currently used as the bottom cell in multijunction space solar cells and could potentially generate approximately 0.5 W/cm² when exposed to a 1000 °C thermal emitter (Fig. 4-a), i.e. 10 times the output of a silicon PV cell under the same conditions. However, present market prices for Ge TPV cells range between 10 and 20 €/cm² (based on quotations from space solar cell manufacturers), roughly 2000–4000 times the cost of a standard silicon PV module.

To reach a cost of about 10 €/W, Ge TPV cells need to produce 1 W/cm², assuming no extra CAPEX costs and a cell cost of 10 €/cm². This is possible when the cells are irradiated by sources at temperatures of at least ~1100 °C, assuming a unity view factor (Fig. 4a and b). Under these conditions, the CAPEX contribution to the levelized costs could be reduced to below 100 €/MWh (Fig. 4c), which falls in the range of grid electricity prices. In such a scenario, even assuming a substantial BOS CAPEX of 10,000 €/m², the total system CAPEX would only increase by 10 %, from 10 €/W to 11 €/W, underscoring the economic advantage of integrating low bandgap TPV cells to boost the power density.

In 2015, the estimated technical potential for industrial waste heat at temperatures above 1000 °C in the EU was approximately 25 TWh/year [40], primarily originating from the steel and iron industries. This estimate assumes that 50 % of the sensible heat in exhaust streams could be technically recovered [41], indicating a total waste heat potential of around 50 TWh/year. Based on the assumption that only 20 % of this energy is recoverable by current TPV systems - i.e., heat retained at temperatures above 1100 °C after recovering the sensible heat for TPV generation - the technical waste heat potential for TPV in the EU is approximately 10 TWh/year. Considering that the EU accounted for only 10 % of global steel production and that steel production has increased by 16 % since 2015, the current global technical potential for waste heat recovery at temperatures exceeding 1100 °C is estimated to surpass 100 TWh/year. With an assumed capacity factor of 80 %, this represents a thermal power capacity of roughly 14 GW and an attainable TPV electric power capacity of around 1 GW, based on an overall thermal-to-electric conversion efficiency between 5 and 10 %.

Realizing this level of power generation would require the production of roughly 100,000 m² of TPV cells, assuming an average power density of 1 W/cm². This demand significantly exceeds the estimated cumulative production of Ge-based space solar cells, currently around 20,000 m² (as discussed in Appendix 2). Therefore, scaling up TPV cell production to meet this demand could lead to significant cost reductions. For example, starting with a current Ge TPV cell cost of 10 €/cm² and assuming a learning rate of 35%—a 35 % reduction in costs for every doubling of cumulative production, similar to advancements in solar PV technologies—the cost of TPV cells could decrease to 3.3 €/cm² once cumulative production reaches 120,000 m². At these cost levels, Ge-based TPV cells could enable levelized electricity costs below 100

Fig. 4. (a) The electric power density, (b) the cost per power capacity (CPP) and (c) the levelized cost of energy (LCOE) of TPV cells as a function of the emitter temperature and cost per area or CPA. Calculations in panel c assume $LCO_{rH} = 0$, so $LCOE_{tpv}$ only accounts for the capital expenditures. In panels a and b, the bands represent bandgap energies ranging from 0.53 eV (lower bound) to 0.74 eV (upper bound). In panel c, the bands represent capacity factors ($CF = t_{eq,tpv} / 8760$) ranging from 50 % (upper bound) to 100 % (lower bound). TPV performance calculations are based on a detailed balance model (published elsewhere [20,24,42]) and assume a grey body emitter with emissivity 0.8, unity view factor, rear reflectance of 90 %, and internal photoluminescence efficiency of 10 %.

€/MWh at temperatures as low as 950 °C, thereby unlocking new market opportunities for TPV technology in waste heat recovery applications.

It is worth noting that, in 2015, the technical waste heat potential in the EU at temperatures ranging from 500 to 1000 °C was estimated at approximately 100 TWh/year [40]—four times greater than the potential at temperatures exceeding 1000 °C. This underscores the importance of developing TPV devices that can operate profitably at lower emitter temperatures, particularly for waste heat recovery applications.

The challenge of achieving low levelized costs of electricity at low emitter temperatures explains why the primary efforts to commercialize TPV solutions for waste heat recovery have focused on near-field TPV devices. This advanced concept, which will be discussed later, enables higher power density generation by maintaining a nano-gap distance between the emitter and the cell. Devices of this kind were developed by MTPVCoop, an MIT spinoff (now defunct), during the first two decades of this century, specifically targeting waste heat recovery applications.

Currently, the TU Dublin spin-off PyramP® is focused on TPV waste heat recovery at higher temperatures using standard (far-field) TPV technology.

3.3. Thermal energy storage

A third potential application of TPV technology lies in thermal energy storage devices, where high-temperature heat is generated through direct solar heating (i.e. concentrated solar power) or surplus electricity from renewable sources like solar PV and wind. This energy input is stored as high-temperature heat and subsequently converted into electricity on demand using TPV technology. In such cases, the radiant thermal energy carries an associated levelized cost (LCOH), highlighting the critical importance of achieving high conversion efficiency.

Fig. 5 illustrates how the levelized cost of TPV electricity varies with the Levelized Cost of Absorbed Radiant Heat (LCO_{rH}) and the capacity factor (CF) of the TPV generator. The figure explores three distinct

Fig. 5. The Levelized Cost of TPV electricity, in €/MWh, as a function of the capacity factor ($CF = t_{eq,tpv} / 8760$) and the levelized cost of absorbed radiant heat (LCO_{rH}) for three scenarios: a) a high-cost ($CPP_{tpv} = 10$ €/W) and high-efficiency ($\eta_{tpv} = 0.4$) TPV cell, representing an InGaAs cell at a current cost of 70 €/cm², operating at an emitter temperature of approximately 1600 °C; b) a low-cost ($CPP_{tpv} = 1$ €/W) and low-efficiency ($\eta_{tpv} = 0.2$) TPV cell, representing a Ge cell at a current cost of 10 €/cm², operating at an emitter temperature of approximately 1600 °C; and c) a low-cost ($CPP_{tpv} = 1$ €/W) and high-efficiency ($\eta_{tpv} = 0.4$) TPV cell, representing an InGaAs cell at a current cost of 70 €/cm², operating at an emitter temperature of approximately 2500 °C. Calculations assume a discount rate of 5 % and 25 years lifetime.

scenarios, each highlighting a different combination of TPV cell cost and efficiency. In the first scenario, depicted in panel a, the TPV system employs a high-cost but high-efficiency InGaAs TPV cell, priced at 70 €/cm² (estimate based on quotations from III-V semiconductors manufacturers) and operating at an emitter temperature of around 1600 °C. Due to its high cost and relatively low emitter temperature, this configuration results in relatively high cost per power capacity (10 €/W) and leveled electricity costs, which are highly sensitive to both the capacity factor and LCO_{RH}.

Panel b illustrates the opposite scenario: a low-cost but low-efficiency TPV system that features a Ge TPV cell priced at 10 €/cm², also operating at an emitter temperature of around 1600 °C. The reduced capital cost (1 €/W) lessens the system's sensitivity to the capacity factor, but its lower efficiency makes it heavily dependent on LCO_{RH}. This emphasizes the importance of minimizing LCO_{RH} to achieve economic competitiveness in this case.

Finally, panel c presents a combination of low cost and high efficiency TPV system, represented by an InGaAs TPV cell priced at 70 €/cm² and operating at a much higher emitter temperature of approximately 2500 °C. The high emitter temperature helps offset the high cost per unit area by increasing power density, resulting in a competitive cost per power capacity of 1 €/W. Additionally, the superior conversion efficiency of the TPV cell enables relatively low leveled costs of TPV electricity across a broad range of LCO_{RH} values. As a result, the system's cost performance becomes less dependent on LCO_{RH}, as described also by Equation (1).

The results in Fig. 5 underscores the key advantage of thermal energy storage applications for TPV technology: the ability to design systems that operate at extremely high temperatures. This design strategy enables state-of-the-art, highly efficient (albeit expensive) TPV cell materials, such as InGaAs, to achieve elevated electric power densities, thereby substantially reducing the capital expenditure component of the leveled cost of electricity. The combination of low cost and high efficiency of InGaAs cells, when irradiated by extreme temperature emitters, leads to a low leveled cost of electricity across a broad range of capacity factors and leveled costs of absorbed radiant heat. Consequently, despite their currently high manufacturing costs, InGaAs cells demonstrate significant potential for economically competitive deployment in ultra-high temperature thermal energy storage systems.

However, the requirement for extreme temperatures imposes constraints on the energy density of sensible heat thermal storage systems. These systems rely on large temperature differences between their charged and discharged states. Given practical limits on maximum thermal storage temperatures and minimum TPV operating temperatures, the effective energy density of the system is confined within this temperature range. A reduction in energy density could increase the cost per unit of energy capacity (CPE), subsequently raising the LCO_{RH}. Latent heat storage systems, on the other hand, provide a constant discharge temperature, but their feasibility is contingent upon the availability of cost-effective and reliable phase change materials (PCMs). These materials limit the range of operable temperatures. Promising candidates, such as silicon and ferrosilicon alloys, have melting points between 1200 °C and 1538 °C. However, these temperatures may still be insufficient to make InGaAs TPV cells economically viable at current costs (as illustrated in Fig. 4c).

A potential solution for operation at lower emitter temperatures is the use of lower-cost, lower-efficiency Ge TPV cells. In particular, these devices could be profitable in systems where released heat is repurposed for domestic hot water or space heating. In this configuration, the reduced thermal-to-electric conversion efficiency of these less expensive TPV cells is offset by their capacity to provide useable heat, leading to a high overall system efficiency. The techno-economic viability of this hybrid combined heat and power (CHP) solution depends on its performance relative to alternative options including conventional batteries and heating technologies such as gas boilers [43], direct electric heaters [30], or heat pumps [44]. Technoeconomic analyses of this hybrid

solution [30,43,44] reveal that recovering waste heat from cell cooling significantly reduces the cost and efficiency constraints on TPV devices. This approach enables the development of economically viable cogeneration systems that operate at moderate temperatures (1200–1500 °C) and integrate TPV technology.

Regardless of the approach chosen, achieving very low LCO_H (and LCO_{RH}) within thermal energy storage devices entails either utilizing direct solar heating [45,46] or harnessing surplus renewable electricity generation as the energy source for heat generation [30,31]. However, due to the inherent efficiency limitations of solar heating, especially losses caused by re-emission in the solar absorber aperture [45,46], attaining very low LCO_H (and LCO_{RH}) at such high temperatures may pose challenges. Conversely, electric-powered systems present advantages such as simpler heating designs and higher charging efficiency. As a result, electric-powered thermal energy storage devices, or TPV batteries, emerge as a promising short-term application. Indeed, the pursuit of TPV batteries has been a key driver of TPV technology advancements in recent years, making this topic particularly deserving of further discussion.

3.4. TPV batteries

TPV batteries represent power-to-heat-to-power storage (PHPS) systems that store electricity in the form of extreme temperature heat (typically in the range of 1200–2500 °C) and convert it back to electricity on demand using TPV. The contribution of the charging power system in these systems can be generally disregarded, given its high efficiency ($\eta_{ch} > 0.9$) and low cost ($CPP_{ht}^* < 0.2$ €/W) for heating elements [30,31]. Additionally, since the surface of the storage media typically serves as the thermal emitter, this cost (CPP_{emit}^*) is already factored into the energy-related subcomponents (CPE^*). Therefore, the primary factors influencing the LCO_{RH} in TPV batteries (see equation (2)) are the price of the electricity input ($LCOE_m$) and the energy-related subcomponents of the system (CPE^*) [30,31].

As an illustrative example, a latent heat TPV battery with a thermal capacity of 10 MWh comprises approximately 8.4 m³ of silicon phase change material (PCM) costing €35,000 at a unit price of €1.8/kg, 3.3 m³ of graphite crucibles priced at €97,000 (€17/kg), and 17 m³ of thermal insulation costing €42,500 (€2.5/L) [30]. This configuration results in an energy subsystem cost of approximately $CPE = €18/\text{kWh}$, considering only the latent heat storage capacity (i.e. neglecting the sensible heat contribution). This subsystem cost corresponds to a CAPEX-component of the leveled cost of radiant heat (LCO_{RH}) of €7.5/MWh, assuming a storage efficiency of 95 %, a TPV thermal efficiency of 90 %, 200 cycles per year, a system lifetime of 25 years, and a discount rate of 5 %. Such a low LCO_{RH} enables competitive values for the leveled cost of TPV electricity (e.g., < €50/MWh) even when using low-cost (1 €/W), low-efficiency (20 %) TPV cells, provided that the charging electricity input cost approaches zero (as shown in panel b of Fig. 5). For low-cost (1 €/W), high-efficiency (40 %) TPV cells, the charging electricity price could remain profitable at values below approximately €10/MWh, as illustrated in panel c of Fig. 5. This highlights the importance of charging the system with surplus electricity at very low prices. Since inexpensive electricity is only available during limited periods, the battery typically needs to be charged at high power rates, leveraging the inexpensive and efficient heating methods commonly employed in such systems.

In addition to achieving a low LCO_{RH}, maintaining a high number of equivalent operating hours for the TPV system (or high capacity factors) is crucial to minimize the cost impact of the TPV generator and ensure the leveled cost remains within profitable margins, as described in Equation (1) and Fig. 5. Having high energy capacity and high energy density is also crucial for minimizing the surface-to-energy storage capacity ratio, thereby reducing the cost of the thermal insulation system [30].

Fig. 6. Stored energy density for the three proposed TPV battery materials: Carbon (C) [49], Silicon (Si) [30,31], and Iron-Silicon-Boron (FeSiB) [30]. Both Si and FeSiB can function as sensible and/or latent heat storage media. Energy densities are calculated assuming a discharged energy state at 500 °C. The energy densities for other discharged energy states can be readily obtained from the figure.

Consequently, optimal TPV batteries are characterized by large energy storage capacities (ideally >10 MWh [30]), infrequent charging cycles throughout the year (fewer than 200 effective cycles per year [44]), high charging power rates (with charging times typically under 5 h [44]), and prolonged discharge durations (typically >10 h [30,44]). In essence, TPV batteries are designed for long-duration storage applications, which have been recognized as a vital asset in the energy system to enable high penetrations of solar and wind in electricity generation [47].

All proposed embodiments of TPV batteries to date adhere to the fundamental principles outlined above. Efforts to reduce the cost of the energy subsystem include the utilization of materials such as liquid silicon [31] or graphite blocks [48] for sensible heat storage, as well as silicon and ferrosilicon alloys for latent heat storage [30]. These materials are notable for their exceptional high energy density (see Fig. 6) and low cost, typically around 5 €/kWh across all cases, though dependent on the operating temperature range (especially for the case of sensible heat storage options).

Between 2018 and 2021, the emergence of TPV battery developers became evident, primarily in the US (Antora Energy and Fourth Power) and Europe (Thermophoton and Silbat). Notably, in 2024, the US-based thermal battery developer Antora Energy announced the establishment of a dedicated InGaAs thermophotovoltaic cell manufacturing line with an annual production capacity of 2 MW [50]. Antora, specializing in carbon-based sensible heat storage systems, has already commissioned a thermal battery and plans to incorporate TPV technology into its operations [51]. Similarly, other TPV battery developers have made significant funding advancements to accelerate their technological progress. In 2024, Fourth Power secured \$19 million to advance its carbon-based, sensible-heat, grid-scale TPV battery development [52]. Meanwhile, in

2022, Thermophoton joined a European Innovation Council-funded program with €5.9 million allocated through the Horizon EU Program to develop latent-heat TPV batteries based on ferrosilicon alloys [53].

In addition to TPV battery developers, other companies like Kraft Block, Rondo, 1414 Degrees, Exergy3, and Electrified Thermal Solutions are targeting thermal energy storage at very high temperatures (>1200 °C) for industrial heat decarbonization [54,55] and are potential candidates for adopting TPV technology in the future. The upcoming deployment of high-temperature thermal batteries for industrial heat decarbonization presents a unique opportunity for TPV technology. Once these systems are in place, integrating a TPV generator into the existing assets would enable the conversion of purely thermal batteries into hybrid systems with electric power capabilities. Consequently, the competitiveness of these batteries will depend primarily on the additional cost of integrating TPV technology, which offers notable advantages over installing entirely new electric energy storage systems. Moreover, thermal batteries provide a controlled high-temperature environment, significantly simplifying the integration and operation of TPV technology compared to other applications, such as waste heat recovery.

The successful application of TPV in thermal energy storage systems could stimulate the mass production of TPV cells. If the total addressable market is confined to industrial heat decarbonization, estimated at 15,900 TWh/year [54,55], the potential TPV market size would be around 1.5 TW_{el}, assuming a capacity factor of 50%, 40% TPV conversion efficiency, and full adoption within these thermal energy storage systems. The market size could expand significantly if TPV technology is also applied to long-duration grid-scale energy storage. Projections suggest that by 2040, long-duration energy storage devices could deploy between 1.5 and 2.5 TW of power capacity [56]. This could lead to a potential demand for TPV generation that, although difficult to quantify, significantly exceeds the estimated 1 GW for waste heat recovery applications at temperatures above 1100 °C (as discussed in section 3.2). Consequently, the opportunities for cost reduction through cumulative production growth and learning curve progression are far greater, potentially accelerating technological advancements, and broaden the scope of potential applications of TPV technology.

4. TPV research challenges

In addition to advancing along the learning curve through the mass production of state-of-the-art TPV cells driven by market applications, TPV technology can also make significant strides through scientific breakthroughs. The overarching objective of TPV research is to render TPV electricity more affordable across a wider range of emitter temperatures. This entails increasing efficiency, enhancing power density, reducing costs, and improving the scalability, reliability and longevity of TPV devices. Table 2 shows a selection of TPV-related concepts aimed at improving four different key aspects of the technology, namely: efficiency, power density, cost per area, and scalability. High-efficiency concepts are particularly relevant for applications with significant leveled costs of radiant heat (LCORH), such as energy storage devices. Conversely, concepts that enable high power density and low cost per area – resulting in a reduced CPI_{tpv}^* – are more important for applications with negligible LCORH and/or limited operating hours, such as waste heat recovery. However, given the current high prices of TPV cells,

Table 2

TPV-related concepts to address each aspect of the technology.

Efficiency	Power density	Cost per area	Scalability
Back surface reflectors	Near-field	Substrate reuse	Dense arrays
Selective emitters	Light-pipe	Cheap substrates	Back contact cells
Front side filters	Hybridization	Cheap absorbers	All-top contact cells
Semi-transparent cells	Low bandgap cells		MIM devices
Bifacial cells	Bifacial cells		
Multijunction cells	Multijunction cells		

enhancing power density and reducing the cost per area remain relevant considerations for all applications. In any case, conducting a quantitative analysis for each specific application, similar to the approach recently presented by Verma et al. [32], is essential to identify which metric is more critical for minimizing the overall LCOE.

4.1. High efficiency

The incorporation of advanced reflectors on the rear side of TPV cells, particularly using the air-bridge configuration [18], has led to recent records in TPV cell efficiency. These reflectors redirect unwanted infrared photons—those the TPV cell cannot convert—back to the emitter, thereby enhancing overall conversion efficiency. When integrated with extremely thin-film ($\sim 1\text{--}2\ \mu\text{m}$) InGaAs semiconductors, these mirrors achieve outband reflectance exceeding 98 %, which has been crucial for achieving over 40 % TPV conversion efficiency at relatively low temperatures of $\sim 1200\ \text{°C}$. This high reflectance is feasible due to the high in-band absorption coefficient of InGaAs, allowing for the use of thin absorbing layers with extremely low out-band absorbance.

An alternative to back surface reflectors could be the use of spectrally selective thermal emitters. These emitters are designed to emit thermal radiation primarily within the spectral response range of the TPV cell while minimizing radiation outside that range, thereby improving overall efficiency. Certain types of selective thermal emitters have achieved remarkably high spectral efficiencies (defined as the ratio of in-band power to total emitted power) up to $\sim 80\%$ [57]. However, a significant challenge remains in ensuring the thermal stability of the materials used. The best-performing selective emitters feature periodic micro-structures composed of distinct materials that must operate at extreme temperatures and withstand thermal cycles. Therefore, these emitters must be meticulously designed to avoid failure mechanisms such as oxidation, grain growth and recrystallization, surface diffusion, and thermal expansion [57,58].

Front-side filters deposited on top of the cell are not constrained by the requirement of material stability at high temperatures, making them an appealing alternative for achieving spectrally selective radiative exchange [57,58]. Depending on the underlying physical mechanism, these filters can be categorized as interference filters, induced transmission filters, plasma filters, or resonant filters based on frequency-selective surfaces [58]. Plasma filters exhibit high in-band absorption, while interference filters are typically optimized for a narrow spectral band or require a large number of dielectric layers, which can introduce significant issues related to cost and design reliability. As a result, the best-performing filters to date often combine different filter types, such as the tandem plasma-interference filter, which achieves spectral efficiencies near 80 % [57].

4.2. High efficiency and power density

Instead of filtering or reflecting light in a selected spectral range, another approach to boost the efficiency involves directly transmitting outband photons through the cell to be re-absorbed in the emitter. Semi-transparent and bifacial [59,60] TPV cells utilize this principle to enhance efficiency beyond the limits of previous designs based on reflectors, filters, and selective emitters. Moreover, bifacial TPV cells [59], designed to be illuminated from both sides, can produce twice as much power as conventional monofacial designs. The challenge lies in cooling the cell, which must rely on edge-cooling arrangements. These cooling strategies can potentially deteriorate the view factor and reduce conversion efficiencies.

Multijunction TPV cells [24] take a different approach by broadening the absorption spectrum of incident light. This is achieved by monolithically stacking at least two sub-cells with different energy bandgaps, each designed to convert a different part of the spectrum with higher efficiency. Dual-junction TPV cells with relatively high bandgaps

(1.4/1.2, 1.2/1.0, 0.85/0.74 eV) have experimentally demonstrated conversion efficiencies around 40 % at temperatures near or beyond $2000\ \text{°C}$ [15,16]. Lower bandgap options (0.74/0.55, 0.72/0.60, and 0.73/0.56 eV) have also been developed [61–63], showing good electrical properties, though their experimental conversion efficiency has not yet been reported.

4.3. High power density

The development of low bandgap TPV cells, either as independent devices or as subcells within a multijunction structure, is essential for boosting power density and enabling the application of TPV technology at lower heat source temperatures (Fig. 4-a), broadening its applications, particularly in waste heat recovery. So far, the InGaAsSb semiconductor (with a bandgap energy of 0.53 eV) is the lowest bandgap material that has enabled a relatively high-performance TPV device operation at room temperature [64]. Prototype TPV cells have been also fabricated on ultra-low bandgap semiconductors like InAs (0.35 eV) [65], and InSb (0.17 eV) [66], but the resultant cells show voltage factors (i.e., open-circuit voltage to bandgap ratio) lower than ~ 0.3 at room temperature, even under high irradiance illumination. As a reference, the expected voltage factor for ideal photovoltaic cells with only radiative recombination, as predicted by detailed balance models [24], exceeds 0.85 for bandgap energies below 0.3 eV when the emitter temperature surpasses $800\ \text{°C}$. This is a fundamental problem linked to the very high non-radiative recombination (mostly Auger) existing in very low bandgap bulk semiconductors. Potential solutions to this issue include the development of quantum nanostructures, like interband cascade TPV cells with InAs/GaSb/AlSb type-II superlattice absorbers [67] or quantum wells based on IV-VI semiconductors [68].

The development of ultra-low bandgap TPV cells is also relevant to the advancement of near-field TPV devices. Near-field TPV devices aim to increase electric power density generation by establishing a nanoscale vacuum gap between the emitter and the TPV cell. This gap allows evanescent waves (photons) to tunnel through and contribute to the generation of electrical power. Several groups have experimentally demonstrated near-field TPV devices [69,70], achieving a record conversion efficiency of 14 % with an electrical power density output of $0.75\ \text{W/cm}^2$ at an emitter temperature of only $457\ \text{°C}$ [71]. This encouraging result suggests significant potential for TPV technology in converting thermal energy at moderate temperatures. However, key factors in achieving this specific result include the cryogenic temperature operation of the InSb (0.17 eV) TPV cell, the very small size of the device (which minimizes ohmic losses), and the use of a micro-positioner (which eliminates the need for nano-spacers and the associated thermal losses). Addressing these limitations is essential for near-field TPV devices to reach practical applications. In this regard, very promising work has been recently reported [72] demonstrating a $0.28\ \text{cm}^2$ near-field TPV device (150 nm gap) generating 1.22 mW at $460\ \text{°C}$.

Another possibility to boost photonic energy transfer without establishing challenging nano gaps involves using light pipes between the emitter and the TPV cell [73,74]. This concept enables approximately 10 times higher electric power density than conventional TPV devices. However, optical absorption and unavoidable thermal conduction losses in the light pipe result in lower conversion efficiencies. Therefore, the primary application of light-pipe TPV devices is in scenarios with negligible leveled cost of heat, such as waste heat recovery. For other applications, further research is needed to develop a highly transparent and thermally insulating light pipe that enables high conversion efficiency.

Alternative solutions to boost the power density of TPV is the hybridization with thermionic [75,76] and thermoelectric generators [77, 78]. Hybridizing with thermionic generators, in particular, could be a solution for addressing scalability challenges in near-field TPV devices [79]. This approach involves establishing a wireless thermionic

connection between the thermal emitter, serving as the thermionic cathode, and the entire front surface of the TPV cell, which functions as the thermionic anode. Experimental validation of this concept using GaAs [76] and InGaAs [80] PV cells demonstrated its effectiveness in eliminating the need for front-side metal grids on the TPV cell. By removing these space-consuming electrodes, this design simplifies integration and theoretically facilitates the development of large-area near-field TPV devices.

4.4. Low cost per area

One of the major drawbacks for wider development of InGaAs TPV devices is the high cost of InP substrates that are needed to epitaxially grow the InGaAs layers. Therefore, the implementation of substrate reuse techniques, such as epitaxial lift-off [81], or the direct growth of InGaAs on cheaper semiconductor substrates, like GaAs [82] or Si [83], is particularly relevant in this case to reduce the cost per unit of area of these devices. This consideration also applies to other TPV cells based on other III-V infrared semiconductors, notably InGaAsSb and GaSb.

Alternatively, some works have attempted to produce TPV cells using cheaper infrared semiconductor materials, notably Germanium [84,85]. However, TPV cells made of Germanium exhibit significantly lower outband reflectance and output voltage, resulting in lower overall efficiency. The lower performance is partially due to germanium's lower absorption coefficient, which necessitates a much thicker absorber layer, leading to substantial outband absorption caused by free carriers. Improving the efficiency of Ge-based TPV cells involves developing thin-film cells or pairing them with spectrally selective emitters or front-side filters, as discussed previously. Other potentially low-cost semiconductor alternatives include GeSn [86], and colloidal quantum dots based on IV-VI group materials like PbS [87] or PbSnSe/PbSrSe quantum wells [68], but none of them have yet demonstrated a high electric performance under TPV operating conditions.

4.5. Scalability

Last but not least, addressing the scalability of TPV technology requires designing large-area TPV generators capable of producing significant power without sacrificing the conversion efficiency of individual cells. This includes developing strategies to assemble TPV cells in dense modules, such as shingling [88], and creating cells better suited for dense interconnection. Examples include cells with alternate polarities [89], all-top-contact cells [90], back contact cells [91], vertical junction cells [92], and, notably, monolithic interconnected modules (MIM) [93]. However, despite these advancements, the demonstration of conversion efficiency in a large TPV module that confirms the scalability potential of TPV technology is still awaited.

5. Conclusions

Thermophotovoltaic technology is expected to play a significant role in the evolving energy landscape, particularly as the electrification of industrial processes gains momentum due to declining electricity prices and the increasing adoption of renewable energy sources. High-temperature thermal energy storage systems, which store surplus electricity as heat, present a particularly promising application for TPV.

The controlled environments provided by high-temperature thermal batteries address many of the challenges previously faced by TPV technology in harsher industrial settings. These advancements create a unique opportunity for TPV to move beyond niche applications and toward broader commercial viability. The potential for TPV technology to achieve high efficiencies and competitive costs, especially in systems designed for extreme temperatures, could catalyze its widespread adoption.

However, realizing this potential will require continued progress along two fronts. On the one hand, mass production and market-driven applications must drive down the costs of TPV cells, enabling the technology to scale effectively. On the other hand, scientific research must continue to push the boundaries of TPV efficiency, power density, and scalability, particularly at lower emitter temperatures.

If these challenges can be met, TPV technology could emerge not only as a key component of high-temperature energy storage solutions but also as a versatile tool for harnessing waste heat and other heat sources across various industries. The combination of market-driven scaling and ongoing research efforts will be essential in unlocking the full potential of TPV as a transformative energy technology.

Footnotes

A preprint article recently published by Verma et al. [32] analyses TPV applications based on LCOE, closely aligning with the approach in this work. The authors declare that, despite the temporal proximity of these studies, both were developed independently, without prior knowledge of each other.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Alejandro Datas: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Paolo Bondavalli:** Writing – review & editing. **Antonio Marco Pantaleo:** Writing – review & editing.

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Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the authors used ChatGPT in order to enhance the clarity and quality of the English language. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Alejandro Datas reports a relationship with Thermophoton that includes: equity or stocks. Alejandro Datas has patent #ES2743794A1 issued to Universidad Politécnica de Madrid. Alejandro Datas has patent #ES2610628A1 issued to Universidad Politécnica de Madrid. Alejandro Datas has patent #ES2584105B2 issued to Universidad Politécnica de Madrid. Alejandro Datas has patent #ES2690162B2 issued to Universidad Politécnica de Madrid. Alejandro Datas has patent #EP3120096B1 issued to Universidad Politécnica de Madrid. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

Grant PID2020-115719RB-C22 funded by MCIN/AEI/ 10.13039/501100011033. Grant 101057954 funded by the European Union.

Appendix 1

The derivation of the expression for $LCOE_{tpv}$ in Equations (1) and (2) involves calculating the CAPEX and OPEX contributions for the entire TPV system. In this work, we present a simplified analytical expression based on several assumptions: constant power operation (i.e., P_{emit} , P_{el} , Q_{in} are constant values), a constant input energy price ($LCOE_{in}$), negligible system degradation, and negligible maintenance costs.

The expression for $LCOE_{tpv}$ indicated in Equations (1) and (2) is derived by expressing the CAPEX, OPEX, and total electricity generated by the system (E_t) as functions of Q_{in} , as shown in Equations (3)–(5) (see Figs. 3 and 7 for a visual representation). The $LCOE_{tpv}$ is then obtained by summing the CAPEX and OPEX contributions and dividing by the total electricity generated, resulting in a final expression that is independent of Q_{in} (Equation (6)). Finally, the annual equivalent hours of operation for the charging (heating) and discharging (TPV) systems are defined respectively as $t_{eq,ht} = Nt_c$ and $t_{eq,TPV} = Nt_d$.

$$CAPEX = CPP_{ht}^* Q_{in} + CPE^* Q_{in} \eta_{ht} t_c + CPP_{emit}^* Q_{in} \eta_{ht} \eta_{st} \frac{t_c}{t_d} + CPP_{tpv}^* Q_{in} \eta_{ht} \eta_{st} \eta_{th} \eta_{tpv} \frac{t_c}{t_d} \tag{3}$$

$$OPEX = LCOE_{in} N_c Q_{in} t_c \tag{4}$$

$$E_t = N_c Q_{in} \eta_{ht} \eta_{st} \eta_{th} \eta_{tpv} t_c \tag{5}$$

$$LCOE_{tpv} = \frac{CAPEX + OPEX}{E_t} = \frac{CPP_{tpv}^*}{\eta_{tpv} \eta_{th}} + \frac{1}{\eta_{tpv} \eta_{th}} \left[\frac{LCOE_{in}}{\eta_{ht} \eta_{st}} + \frac{CPP_{ht}^*}{\eta_{ht} \eta_{st} t_{eq,ht}} + \frac{CPE^*}{\eta_{st} N_c} + \frac{CPP_{emit}^*}{t_{eq,TPV}} \right] \tag{6}$$

Fig. 7. An example of dynamic operation of a TPV system incorporating thermal energy storage. Input (charging) power is represented by positive values, while output (discharging) power is represented by negative values. Each cycle consists of a charging phase of duration t_c and a discharging phase of duration t_d , repeated over N_c cycles.

Appendix 2. Estimation of Ge-based space solar cells production volume

The cumulative production volume of Ge-based space solar cells has been estimated using publicly available data from leading manufacturers, specifically Spectrolab and Azur Space. Notably, Spectrolab reported a production output of 200 kW in 2009, equivalent to approximately 530 m² of solar cells [94]. Their cumulative production surpassed 4 MW, totaling around 6.5 million cells [95], corresponding to an estimated surface area of 10,000 m². Similarly, Azur Space, reported accumulated delivery of more than 1.5 million multijunction cells [96], corresponding to around 4000 m² of solar cells. Additionally, Azur Space cited a production capacity of 500,000 wafers per year [97], representing between 4000 and 8000 m², depending on whether 4-inch or 6-inch wafers are used. Combining these figures, the total cumulative production volume is estimated to be around 20,000 m². Furthermore, current production estimates for Ge-based III-V space solar cells suggest an annual output of approximately 1000 m², assuming a market volume of 500 kW/year. However, the maximum production capacity could significantly exceed this figure, potentially surpassing 10,000 m²/year.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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